

THE EXTENT OF PARTICIPATION OF LGBTQIA+ STUDENTS IN ACADEMIC PROGRAMS AND NON-ACADEMIC ACTIVITIES OF THE UNIVERSITIES IN BUTUAN CITY

Rhegzjoy G. Acompañado

Mater of Arts in Education, Agusan Colleges Incorporated,
Butuan City, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10301078>

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to investigate the extent of participation of LGBTQIA+ students in academic programs and non-academic activities of the universities in Butuan City during the school year 2022-2023. It further looked into the differences in gender preferences, age, sex, year level, and course. The quantitative research design was utilized, employing the researcher-made questionnaire for data gathering. A total of 74 respondents from Father Saturnino Urios University and Caraga State University were chosen through snowball sampling. The ANOVA was employed to determine the significant difference in participation in academic programs and non-academic activities when respondents were grouped according to profile. The study found that in academic programs, LGBTQIA+ students were highly participative in group work activities, while in non-academic activities, LGBTQIA+ students were just merely for enjoyment as part of the university. The findings also revealed that there is no significant difference in participation in academic programs and non-academic activities across different ages and gender preferences. In terms of year level, there is a significant difference in participation in academic programs while there is no significant difference in participation in non-academic activities. From the findings, the researcher proposes an action plan-related activity recommend to Gender and Development Program to educate and elevate awareness of LGBTQIA+ existence and gender preference in the context of sexual orientation, gender identity, and expression.

Keywords: *LGBTQIA+ students, Student Participation, Academic, Non-academic*

INTRODUCTION

In the Philippine setting, lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer, intersex, and asexual (LGBTQIA+) students are now visible at any state universities and colleges. Students' involvement in academic programs and non-academic activities is crucial. As defined by Holdsworth (2000), student participation is involvement in the classroom and extracurricular activities on the school campus. However, one of the challenges for LGBTQIA+ students to succeed in academics is gender bias and bullying experiences inside the premises Kay (2022).

In CHED Memorandum Order No. 1, Series of 2015, there were several clauses on gender equality and mainstreaming, but LGBTQIA+ students are still vulnerable to

different challenges and hesitate to participate in activities due to possible ramifications such as bullying and discrimination on the university campus (Burnes & Singh, 2016). Thus, LGBTQIA+ students' participation in academic programs and non-academic activities is the most challenging part because their gender preferences do not conform to the hetero-normative standard that has been usually practiced in education.

According to Flores (2019), revealed that the Philippines ranked 28th in a year from 2004 to 2017 on social acceptance of (LGBT) people using the Global Acceptance Index (GAI) score out of 174 countries. But still, some predicaments of LGBTQIA+ students may be happening continuously inside and outside school and remain visible, which personally causes people's anxiety about achieving gender equality (Schwartz & Sinicrope, 2013).

The United Nations Development Program and United States Agency for International Development (UNDP and USAID, 2014) state that academic freedom includes the right of the school to decide the rules and policies. However, academic freedom affected the negative experiences of many lesbians, gays, bisexuals, and transgender (LGBT) Filipinos in educational institutions. In addition, McElhill, (2006) states that Filipino people in schools sadly remained gender-insensitive to the new curriculum, such as the culture of bullying and the existence of anti-LGBT policies, e.g., one of the policies required haircuts and masculinity tests conducted by some higher education institutions.

Notwithstanding, numerous studies have emerged to provide rich information about LGBTQIA+ individuals, but the particular challenges and experiences of their participation in academic programs and non-academic activities were not targeted. Mainly, the purpose of this research study is to determine the extent of participation in academic programs and non-academic activities and the challenges encountered by LGBTQIA+ students in their participation in academic programs and non-academic activities in the school learning environment. This study provides a better understanding with its informative facts that will serve as an educational context to shed some light on what policies and activities can be proposed for the GAD program in the universities.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework of the Study

This study was anchored on two theoretical frameworks, namely, Queer Theory by Judith Butler (1988) and Theory of Involvement by Alexander Astin (1999). The first theory underpinning a research study was called Queer theory, which states that it is an academic discipline that concentrates on non-normative sexuality and gender identity in a normative way of thinking among individuals through influential factors of power in order to stabilize certain norms in society. As simplified by Creswell (2010), Queer theory focused on individuals calling themselves lesbians, gays, or transgendered people, or more specifically, those individuals who are on the LGBTQIA+ spectrum. This approach did not objectify individuals; however, it concerned the impacts of cultural and political means and the conveyed voices and experiences of individuals who have been suppressed in general. The author's concept has more significance in understanding the existing LGBTQIA+ preferences as far as participating and learning in academic programs and non-academic activities are concerned at the tertiary level of education.

To get the gist of Judith Butler's ideology, the Queer theory perspective emphasizes gender beyond the usual definition of gender as a noun but rather as a verb that portrays specific actions to determine a certain individual's gender. According to Butler (1988), our understanding of gender is based on the performative concept of Gender-performativity. The concept of gender performative explained that there was no real authentic performance of gender but rather all gender was imitation and copy. In other words, gender was performative through masculinity and femininity in order to determine individuals' gender preferences. The essential meaning of the performative concept of gender is not about what a person is but what a person can do. Another key to Queer theory was dismantling the hetero-nominative perception that our natural form of attraction was only between a man and a woman.

According to the collaborative study of Barker & Scheele (2016) and Jagose (1996), as cited by Foreman (2018), Queer theory rethinks the misconceptions and perceptions about gender, sex, and sexuality that are defined as socially constructed. This would simply mean that sex was a biological distinction and all genders existing were fluids, a misconception targeted by Queer theory to debunk, such as that sex was fixed, static, and unchanging throughout their lives, whereas gender was a behavioral component, observable, and learned from the social environment.

Moreover, to support the idea that gender is socially constructed, Butler's perspective pointed out a certain idea that helped define the distinction between sex and gender in a certain context. To simplify the definition of how these two words, such as sex and gender, differ from each other. According to Rubin (1984), as cited by Kang et al. (2017), the two distinctive categories of sex and gender are defined through the set of arrangements by which a society converts biological sexuality into the products of human activity. From Rubin's perspective, sex referred to male and female, but the determinant was linked to biology, and gender referred to masculine and feminine, but the social construct was totally based in culture.

The second theory that underpinned the study was the Theory of Involvement. According to Astin (1984), for student growth to take place, students need to actively engage in their environment. This involvement requires the amount of physical and psychological energy that students devote to the academic experience. The Astin model consists of inputs, environment, and outcomes (IEO) models. Inputs categorized the student's demographics, background, and any previous experiences. Environment unfolded experiences that the LGBTQIA+ students would have been experiencing in their college journey. The outcome would be based on the number of LGBTQIA+ students who will be promoted to the next level and the number of graduates in spite of the challenges they have encountered.

The following theories can be related by looking at the different focused variables of the study. By the lens of Queer theory, the true identity of respondents are determine which spectrum in an acronym of LGBTQIA they belong and to recognize as they are members of the LGBTQIA+ community. In detailed information, this theory relates to these variables such as Sex Assigned At Birth (SAAB): Male and Female, and Gender Preferences: Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer, Intersex and Asexual (LGBTQIA) spectrum which can be noted in the demographic profile of the respondents. On the other hand, Theory of Involvement relates to these variables such as the extent of participation of the LGBTQIA+ students in academic programs and non-academic activities and the challenges encountered by the respondents in participation in academic programs and non-academic activities in the universities.

To simplify, the two variables are categorized as dependent and independent variables. In dependent variables, these variables are refer to the extent of participation of the LGBTQIA+ students activities under the academic programs and extracurricular activities in the non-academic. However, students' involvements are classified into academic programs and non-academic activities. In addition, the challenges experienced by LGBTQIA+ students can be determined by their participation in academic programs and non-academic activities in the school's learning environment.

The independent variables are focused on the following: sex assigned by birth: male and female; present gender preference: lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer, intersex, and asexual; year level: first year, second year, third year, and fourth year; and pursued academic program. The process that represents how these independent variables bring effects to the dependent variables in order to draw the findings of what policy and activity can be proposed to the existing GAD Program at the two universities is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Research Paradigm of the Study

Research Questions

This study assessed the extent of participation of the Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer, Intersex and Asexual or LGBTQIA+ students in academic programs and non-academic activities of the universities in Butuan City in the School Year 2022-2023.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions.

1. What is the demographic profile of respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Sex Assigned At Birth;
 - 1.2 Present Gender Preference;
 - 1.3 Age Group;
 - 1.4 Year level;
 - 1.5 Pursued Academic Program?
2. What is the extent of participation of the students in terms of the following?
 - 2.1 Academic Program; and
 - 2.2 Non-academic activities?
3. What is the extent of manifestation of the challenges encountered by the respondents in their participation in the academic program and non-academic activities of the universities?
4. Is there a significant difference in the extent of participation of the students in the academic program and non-academic activities when they are grouped according to profile?
5. On the basis of findings of the study, what activities and policy recommendation can be proposed to Gender and Development Program?

Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant difference in the extent of participation of the LGBTQIA+ students in the academic program and non-academic activities when grouped according to profile.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-quantitative research design. According to Creswell (2013), quantitative design emphasizes objective measurements, statistical, mathematical, and numerical analysis of data collected through polls, questionnaires, and surveys, or by manipulating preexisting statistical data using computational techniques. Consequently, it was appropriate for the study, as it concentrates on gathering numerical data and generalizing it across groups of people or explaining a particular phenomenon. Given that descriptive research's primary goal was to determine the traits, frequencies, patterns, and categories of the variables, it was chosen as an appropriate approach for the research study.

This research design conducted through online survey. According to Narayanaswamy & Harinarayana (2016), concluded that online surveys or web-based surveys have become convenient because of the lesser cost of administering questionnaires, the ability to reach out to a large population, geographical and temporal advantages, reaching a unique individual, and other benefits. By doing this, the researcher ensured ethical consideration, trust, confidentiality, and privacy for the details and information provided by the respondents.

The researcher utilized the method of a survey questionnaire. According to Gay (1987), the survey method is the most frequently used type of self-research report. It provided an opportunity for the researcher to collect data from a population and determine the current status of the population, especially if there were one or more needed variables. The survey method used was a scale survey, as it required less time and was less expensive. The questionnaire was personally administered by the researcher and given

to the respondents to the study. But in some other way, this could be usually mailed, and there are some options to direct the respondents using the digital platforms.

Research Locale

The following research locales are presented: Father Saturnino Urios University (FSUU) and Caraga State University (CSU). These two universities were known and popular tertiary schools in Butuan City. The Father Saturnino Urios University, or FSUU, was located at JC Aquino Avenue Street, while, the Caraga State University-Main Campus, or CSU, was located at Brgy. Ampayon in Butuan City, Province of Agusan Del Norte, Caraga Region.

The building structures of these universities were both separately located in Butuan City, Caraga Region, Agusan Del Norte. However, these two universities, particularly; the Father Saturnino Urios University (FSUU) and Caraga State University-Main Campus (CSU), both have passable roads as their locations are along the National Highway that has 12 minutes of travel time from the main city where the Father Saturnino Urios University (FSUU) is located to Caraga State University-Main Campus (CSU). When it comes to the distance area, from the starting point at Father Saturnino Urios University (FSUU), which is located at San Francisco Street, Butuan City, travel to Caraga State University (CSU), which is located at Brgy. Ampayon along the National Highway, KM 7, NH1, has a distance of exactly 6.7 km.

The following are the research locales' presented in an organize Map of the two universities in Butuan City: the Father Saturnino Urios University (FSUU) and the Caraga State University (CSU) are shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3.

Figure 2. Map of Father Saturnino Urios University (FSUU) in Butuan City
 Legend: ●

Figure 3. Map of Caraga State University (CSU)-Main Campus in Butuan City
 Legend:

Population and Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study comprised lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer, intersex, and asexual or LGBTQIA+ students from two universities in Butuan City. The 74 respondents were determined through their characteristics of present gender preferences and categorized by sex assigned at birth, year level, pursued academic program, LGBTQIA+ student participation in academic programs and nonacademic activities, and challenges encountered in participating in academic programs and non-academic activities as part of the survey questionnaire administered by the researcher. As to the distribution of the respondents, 85.1% or 63 out of 74 respondents, were from the Caraga State University, or CSU, and 14.9% or 11 out of 74 respondents, were from the Father Saturnino Urios University, or FSUU. The majority of the respondents were LGBTQIA+ students at Caraga State University.

Sample Design

The researcher for the study utilized snowball sampling, a non-probability sampling technique that was appropriate to the study. According to Glen (2022), snowball sampling was a research technique for gathering data where participants in the research recruited other participants to participate in a test survey. It was a more applicable design for the study since respondents such as lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer, intersex, and asexual students were limited in these particular areas. In fact, no demographic or statistical record can be found at present, not even for the two universities. Theoretically, the process of using snowball sampling was that once the ball started rolling, it picked up more snow along the way and became larger. There were two steps to be applied during the survey: identify the potential subjects in the population; one or two subjects can be initially found and asked to recruit other respondents. These steps were repeated until the needed sample size was reached.

The researcher has used own judgment to choose the respondents who answered the survey questionnaire. The sample size population was categorized through their characteristics: sex assigned at birth, age, present gender preference, year level (first year, second year, third year, and fourth year), and their pursued academic program. In these variables, the inclusion criteria in selecting respondents were taken through the design of snowball sampling, and the target population was a maximum of seventy-four (74) LGBTQIA+ students from the two selected universities in Butuan City.

Research Instrument

The researcher made questionnaire was composed of two parts, specifically Part I (demographic profile) and Part II (survey questionnaire), to ensure the richness of the data. Part I was the demographic profile with checklists and blanks to be filled out by the respondents in terms of sex assigned at birth, present gender preference, year level, and pursued academic program. Next, in Part II, was the survey questionnaire, which comprised a five-point Likert scale for the respondents' answers with the use of a checklist. However, all answers from the respondents as a set of observations can be measured through the statistical tool used by the researcher in the study.

Validation of Research Instrument

In this part, the researcher used a research instrument to conduct a survey of the subject respondents at the two universities. Prior to the formal steps in conducting a survey with the subject respondents, the researcher would follow ethical considerations to ensure the safety and confidentiality of the respondents. In doing so, the researcher prepared important tools for the survey, such as a letter of request, a letter of consent, a letter of approval, and a content validation of the research instrument to be approved by the three experts.

For the survey questionnaire, two parts were used, such as a Google Form link for the virtual survey and a hard copy of the survey questionnaire for the physical survey. With regards to the validation of the research instrument, the researcher wrote a letter of request to be sent to the three experts knowledgeable of the topic. Since the study was related to gender studies, specifically LGBTQIA+ students' participation in academic programs and non-academic activities, However, the researcher decided to choose three experts: one expert can relate to the topic of language and culture; another expert has an extensive background on gender and development as a former Head Coordinator of the Gender and Development Program at Bukidnon State University-Main Campus; and one expert has been taught gender and society as a current Professor IV at Central Mindanao University.

This research instrument was validated at first before proceeding to conduct a digital survey of the subject respondents in the two universities, particularly at Father Saturnino Urios University and Caraga State University in Butuan City. In terms of the reliability and validity of the research instrument, the researcher has successfully conducted a try-out test for thirty (33) LGBTQIA+ individuals who are not students to answer the survey questionnaire completely.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher of the study ensured ethical consideration for the implementation of the data gathering procedure. The researcher obtained the approval of the research committee of Agusan Colleges Incorporated (ACI) before conducting the survey. Upon approval of the request for a survey, the researcher prepared the informed consent for the respondents to the study. This study focused on the extent of participation of LGBTQIA+ students in academic programs and non-academic activities at the two universities. The selection of respondents was limited since there were no groups of LGBTQIA+ students formally recognized at the two universities.

In data gathering, the researcher integrated a digital platform as the most convenient way to connect with and contact LGBTQIA+ students as subject respondents of the study. For instance, the researcher used digital platforms such as Facebook and Google Forms to send links to the respondents from these two universities, particularly Father Saturnino Urios University and Caraga State University in Butuan City. In this alternative, social media sites such as Facebook and Google Form links were utilized by the researcher. According to Franz et al. (2019), social media platforms provided an information-rich opportunity to reach diverse populations that would otherwise be difficult to identify. In that case, Facebook was the most dominant player in the social media landscape.

The survey was conducted virtually at the most convenient time for the respondents, using their Facebook accounts and group chats. The researcher was created a private Google Form link to explain the overview and the primary purpose of the survey to the respondents.

The Google Form link comprised two parts: Part 1. Demographic Profile and Part 2 Survey Questionnaire. After answering the demographic profile and survey questionnaire, the respondents completely submitted their respective responses. Once completed, respondents received duplicate answers with the certificate of participation in their respective emails.

Scoring and Quantification of Data

Part I, the Demographic Profile of the Respondents: Sex Assigned At Birth; Male and Female, Present Gender Preference; Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer, Intersex, and Asexual. Institutions: Father Saturnino Urios University, or FSUU, and Caraga State University, Main Campus, or CSU. Age range: 18 to 21, 23 to 26, 27 to 30, 31 to 35, and 36 and up. Year level: first year, second year, third year, and fourth year.

In Part II, the researcher utilized a 5-point Likert scale that ranges from 1.0–1.49 strongly disagree, which was interpreted as very low; 1.5–2.49 disagree, which was

interpreted as low; 2.50–3.49 undecided, which was interpreted as uncertain; 3.50–4.49 agree, which was interpreted as high; and 4.5–5.00 strongly agree, which was interpreted as very high. The results are added in order to get the total weight scores.

Statistical Treatment

The data was tabulated, organized, and presented through tables. However, all variables, such as nominal, ordinal, and categorical, in quantitative data were statistically treated, analyzed, and interpreted using the statistical tools that fit the study. The following statistical tools were employed:

The frequency and percentage were used to measure the distribution of variables such as sex assigned at birth, present gender preference, age group, year level, and pursued academic program. The mean and standard deviation were utilized in order to measure the distribution of the set of variables. The mean is the sum of the set of observations divided by the number of that particular set of observations. The weighted mean is the formula that can be used in order to measure the set of particular observations. This is important in order to get the total average of a particular set of observations. The standard deviation is one of the measures of variations to find out how spread-out the numbers are from the given variables, and this can be taken through the square root of the variance.

The ANOVA was employed in order to find out if there is a significant difference between LGBTQIA+ students in the extent of participation in academic and non-academic activities when they are grouped according to their profile.

RESULTS

As to the frequency distribution of sex assigned at birth. It showed that 59 out of 74 respondents were male (79.7%), and 15 out of 74 respondents were female (20.3%). The data supported the fact that the majority of the respondents were male from Caraga State University, or CSU, and Father Saturnino Urios University, or FSUU. This means that male students were more dominant than female students. This can be implied that, in relation to their gender preferences, the majority of the respondents were gays, bisexuals, and transgender women.

The frequency distribution of respondents as to their present gender preferences. On the spectrum of LGBTQIA+, it was shown that the highest percentage in terms of gender preference was gay, with 23 frequency counts, which represents 31.1%. Followed by 21 transgender and 21 lesbian, which represent the same percentage value of 28.4%; and 4 bisexual, which represents 5.4%. The respondents whose present gender preferences are asexual and queer have the same percentage value of 2.7% with two frequency counts. Pansexual preference has the lowest percentage with 1.4%, which is 1 out of 74 LGBTQIA+ students.

The frequency distribution of respondents in terms of age. It is shown that aging 18–22 years old has the highest percentage with 67.7%, which is 50 out of 74 LGBTQIA+ students, and aging 36 years old and above has the lowest percentage with 2.7%, which is 2 out of 74 LGBTQIA+ students when they are grouped according to the age that they presently claim.

The frequency distribution of respondents according to their year level. It showed that 26 out of 74 respondents were in their fourth year, which has the highest percentage of 35.1%, and 13 out of 74 respondents were in their second year, which has the lowest percentage of 17.6%. This can be inferred from the fact that the majority of the respondents were graduating students.

The frequency distribution in terms of pursued academic programs at Caraga State University. It showed that the highest percentage value was 27.7%, in which 19 out of 74 respondents were taking a Bachelor of Science in Forestry. 1 out of 74 respondents, representing 1.4%, took a Bachelor of Science in Applied Mathematics or a Bachelor of Science in Philippine Literature.

On other hand, at Father Saturnino Urios University, it showed that the highest percentage value was 2.7%, in which 2 out of 74 respondents were taking the following courses: Bachelor of Science in Education and Bachelor of Arts in Political Science, respectively. The lowest percentage value was 1.4%, in which 1 out of 74 respondents was taking the following courses: Bachelor of Science in Engineering, Bachelor of Science in Business Administration, Bachelor of Science in Nursing, Bachelor of Arts in Communication, Bachelor of Science in Hotel and Restaurant Management, Bachelor of Science in Accountancy, and Bachelor of Science in Information Technology.

Based on the data, this can be observed that in the Caraga State University (CSU) and the Father Saturnino Urios University (FSUU), LGBTQIA+ individuals are visibly existing at this present school year. This means that their existence is inevitable and there is more probability that their population will increase from these two universities. Thus, this can be inferred from the fact that there is a great possibility that LGBTQIA+ individuals will encounter alienation of social isolation.

DISCUSSION

Table 1

Mean Distribution of the Extent of Participation of LGBTQIA+ students in Academic Programs

Indicators	Wtd Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
Q1. I am always present in my attendance in the class.	4.77	.424	Strongly Agree	Very High
Q2. I participate in the group work activity.	4.80	.405	Strongly Agree	Very High
Q3. I initiate the conversation with other classmates.	4.54	.601	Strongly Agree	Very High
Q4. I answer questions from the teacher during the class activity.	4.54	.591	Strongly Agree	Very High
Q5. I interact with my classmates within the classroom.	4.49	.801	Agree	High
Q6. I contribute my idea during the class discussions.	4.58	.641	Strongly Agree	Very High
Q7. I cooperate with my classmates in the class activity.	4.70	.460	Strongly Agree	Very High
Q8. I ask my class instructor for permission when it is needed.	4.68	.471	Strongly Agree	Very High
Q9. I assist my classmates when they ask for help.	4.65	.508	Strongly Agree	Very High
Q10. I enjoy being a part of the class.	4.68	.499	Strongly Agree	Very High
Q11. I build friendships with my classmates.	4.59	.618	Strongly Agree	Very High
Q12. I perform my roles and function in the classroom.	4.65	.508	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall Weighted Mean	4.64	.382	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend: 1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree/ Very Low; 1.50-2.49-Disagree/Low; 2.50-3.49 Undecided/Uncertain;3.50-4.49-Agree/High; 4.50-5.00-Strongly Agree/Very High

Table 1 shows the mean distribution of the extent of participation of LGBTQIA+ students in academic programs. The analysis yielded the highest weighted mean of 4.80 and .405 standard deviation, respectively. It can be observed that the majority of LGBTQIA+ students strongly agreed, which was interpreted as very high. Thus, it can be inferred that in the academic programs, the LGBTQIA+ students highly participated in the group work activity inside the classroom.

On the other hand, one indicator represents the lowest value of a 4.49 weighted mean and an 8.01 standard deviation, respectively. It can be observed that some of the LGBTQIA+ students agreed, which is interpreted as high. This means some LGBTQIA+

students are not interacting with their classmates during their participation in academic activities. Thus, it can be inferred that some LGBTQIA+ students hesitated to communicate with their classmates when participating in academic activities within the classroom.

This holds true to Burnes & Singh (2016), stated that the LGBTQIA+ students were hesitated to participate in the activity due to the possible ramifications of bullying and discrimination. McElhill (2006), believed that there were Filipino people who sadly remained gender-insensitive to the present curriculum, such as the culture of bullying and the existence of anti-LGBT policies in schools, and Rankin et al. (2010), mentioned that LGBTQ students will be negatively labeled because of their different gender preferences, and also, according to Munyuki & Vincent (2018), some other way of invulnerability as their coping mechanism to lessen communication in order to have a lack of personal connection to their classmates just to hide their present gender preferences.

Table 2

Mean Distribution of the Extent of Participation of the LGBTQIA+ students in Non-academic Activities

Indicators	Wtd Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
Q1.I perform my roles and function within the school campus.	4.49	.798	Strongly Agree	Very High
Q2. I communicate with other teachers,students, and non-teaching personnel when it is needed.	4.54	.554	Strongly Agree	Very High
Q3. I initiate conversations with other students on the school campus.	4.32	.813	Agree	High
Q4. I answer questions from the teachers, students, and non-teaching personnel when someone asks me within the school.	4.58	.524	Strongly Agree	Very High
Q5. I interact with other students on the campus.	4.42	.722	Agree	High
Q6. I participate in school activities and events inside the campus.	4.53	.646	Strongly Agree	Very High
Q7. I contribute the idea to other students during a group discussion with different courses.	4.49	.667	Agree	High
Q8. I cooperate with other student organizations in the university.	4.53	.602	Strongly Agree	Very High
Q9. I enjoy being a part of the university.	4.77	.424	Strongly Agree	Very High
Q10. I build friendships with other students from different courses.	4.55	.665	Strongly Agree	Very High
Q11.The school activities develop my confidence, talents, and social and communication skills.	4.54	.554	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall Weighted Mean	4.53	.463	Strongly Agree	Very High

Legend: 1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree/ Very Low; 1.50-2.49-Disagree/Low; 2.50-3.49-Undecided/Uncertain; 3.50-4.49-Agree/High; 4.50-5.00-Strongly Agree/Very High

Table 2 displays the results of the mean and standard deviation, which were employed to find out if there was any participation of LGBTQIA+ students when they asked according to their participation in extracurricular activities. The analysis yielded a statistical value of 4.53 overall weighted mean with a standard deviation of .463 for the non-academic activities, which was interpreted as very high. This can be inferred from the fact that the LGBTQIA+ students participated in non-academic activities.

As indicated in the data, the analysis yielded the highest value of 4.77 weighted mean and .424 standard deviation, respectively. This means that the LGBTQIA+ students have enjoyed being a part of the university. On the other hand, three indicators have the lowest value, such as; I initiate conversations with other students on the school campus, I interact with other students on the campus, and I contribute the idea to other students during a group discussion with different courses, where students agreed, which represents a high interpretation. This implied that, in the aspect of non-academic

activities, some of them are not initiating conversations with others, interacting with other students on campus, or contributing ideas to other students during a group discussion.

According to Munyuki & Vincent (2018), LGBTQIA+ students find alternatives to face the alienation of social isolation, such as acquiescence, invulnerability, verbal action, and resistance. Acquiescence: the LGBTQIA+ learner should find ways to fit into the strict gender binary of male and female so that cisgender people do not identify LGBTQIA+ students as other individuals. Invulnerability, simply means to lessen your communication with classmates or roommates to make a lack of personal connection. Verbal action, let LGBTQIA+ students stand for themselves and repulse any negative behavior that may be felt by them. Resistance means that there was a need to adapt to the neutral space and vast diversity in spite of the existence of different cultures inside the school campus. All of these alternatives could be seen on campus, where students must find ways to overcome challenges in the school.

Table 3

Extent of Manifestation of the Challenges encountered by the LGBTQIA+ students in their participation in academic programs and non-academic activities in the Caraga State universities

Indicators	Wtd Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
#1 I'm not free to come out with my present Preference publicly in the classroom and school activities participation.	2.92	1.248	Strongly Disagree	Very Low
#2. I hesitate to discuss my gender preference when my classmates, fellow students, instructors, counselors, non-teaching personnel and staff ask me publicly or privately.	3.03	1.307	Strongly Disagree	Very Low
#3. I can't speak up when my classmates, fellow students, instructors, non-teaching personnel and staff automatically decline the students' participation in class and school activities.	2.84	1.260	Strongly Disagree	Very Low
#4. I hear disparaging remarks from my classmates, fellow students, instructors, non-teaching personnel, and staff, whether the comments are innocently, jokingly, or maliciously.	3.05	1.084	Strongly Disagree	Very Low
#5. I doubt participating in some activities related to academic and non-academic programs in the school campus.	2.94	1.216	Strongly Disagree	Very Low
#6. My present preference hinders to participate in academic and non-academic activities in school.	2.89	1.246	Strongly Disagree	Very Low
#7. I choose to hide my present preference during my participation in academic and non-academic activities.	2.62	1.325	Strongly Disagree	Very Low
#8. I'm not experiencing humiliation, rejection, Ostracism in participating the school activities.	3.43	1.187	Strongly Disagree	Very Low
Overall weighted Mean	2.75	.925	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Legend: 1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree/ Very Low; 1.50-2.49-Disagree/Low; 2.50-3.49-Undecided/Uncertain; 3.50-4.49 Agree/High; 4.50-5.00-Strongly Agree/Very High

Table 3 displays the results of the mean and standard deviation, which were statistically used to determine the extent of manifestation of challenges encountered by the LGBTQIA+ students in their participation when they were asked according to their participation in academic programs and non-academic activities. The analysis yielded an overall weighted mean of 2.75 and a standard deviation of .925 for academic programs and non-academic activities, respectively. This can be shown by the fact that the majority of LGBTQIA+ students strongly disagreed, which interpreted a very low on the extent of

manifestation of challenges encountered during their participation in academic and non-academic activities.

This very low interpretation means that there are no instances of manifestations of challenges encountered by LGBTQIA+ students in their participation in academic programs and non-academic activities at the university. However, this interpretation profoundly implies that Caraga State University is open to LGBTQIA+ students and that their different gender preferences are not a hindrance to participating in academic programs and non-academic activities. This can be inferred from the fact that, in aspects of academic programs and non-academic activities, LGBTQIA+ students participation is highly observed.

Participating in academic programs and non-academic activities is an essential part of college life for college students in order to have a better learning experience. According to Knight & Wood (2005) and Cohen (2008), student participation is a key to better academic learning, and Bekkering & Ward (2020) help students develop their skills and qualities by dealing with logistical issues, building their confidence, and creating a good connection with their instructors, as all these things have a significant impact for them.

Table 4

Extent of Manifestation of the Challenges encountered by the LGBTQIA+ students in their participation in academic programs and non-academic activities in Father Saturnino Urios University

Indicators	Wtd Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Interpretation
#1. I'm not free to come out with my present preference publicly in the classroom and school activities participation	3.18	1.537	Disagree	Low
#2. I hesitate to discuss my gender preference when my classmates, fellow students, instructors, counselors, non-teaching personnel, and staff ask me publicly or privately.	3.18	1.401	Strongly disagree	Very low
#3. I can't speak up when my classmates, fellow students, instructors, non-teaching personnel, and staff automatically decline the students' participation in class and school activities.	3.09	1.446	Strongly disagree	Very low
#4. I hear disparaging remarks from my classmates, fellow students, instructors, non-teaching personnel, and staff, whether the comments are innocently, jokingly, or maliciously.	3.73	1.191	Strongly disagree	Very low
#5. I doubt participating in some activities related to academic and non-academic programs in the school campus.	3.09	1.446	Strongly disagree	Very low
#6. My present preference hinders to participate in academic and non-academic activities in school.	3.00	1.732	Strongly disagree	Very low
#7. I choose to hide my present preference during my participation in academic and non-academic activities.	3.36	1.502	Disagree	Low
#8. I'm not experiencing humiliation, rejection, or ostracism in participating the school activities.	3.27	1.489	Strongly disagree	Very low
Overall weighted Mean	3.10	1.094	Strongly disagree	Very low

Legend: 1.00-1.49-Strongly Disagree/ Very Low; 1.50-2.49-Disagree/Low; 2.50-3.49-Undecided/Uncertain; 3.50-4.49-Agree/High; 4.50-5.00-Strongly Agree/Very High

Table 4 highlights the results of the mean and standard deviation, which were employed to determine if there were manifestations of challenges encountered by the LGBTQIA+ students in their participation in academic programs and non-academic activities when they were asked according to their participation. The analysis yielded an overall weighted mean of 3.10 and a standard deviation of 1.094 in participation for academic programs and non-academic activities, respectively. This means that the

majority of LGBTQIA+ students strongly disagreed, which interpreted a very low manifestation of challenges encountered during participation in academic programs and non-academic activities.

Although the result had a very low interpretation, it does not mean that there are no instances of manifestation of challenges encountered by LGBTQIA+ students. However, there were two indicators yielded values of 3.18 weighted mean with 1.537 standard deviation and 3.36 weighted mean with 1.502 standard deviation represented low interpretation, respectively. This means that some LGBTQIA+ students encountered manifestations of challenges because of their present gender preferences; they were not free to come out with their present gender preferences publicly in the classroom and school activities, and they chose to hide their present preferences during participation in academic and non-academic activities. Thus, it can be inferred that gender preference is one of the manifestation of challenges encountered by LGBTQIA+ students in participation in academic programs and non-academic activities in the university.

In such a situation, hiding their present gender preferences is used as a coping mechanism in order to participate in the activities. According to Munyuki & Vincent (2018), LGBTQIA students applied alternative ways to face alienation and isolation, such as acquiescence, invulnerability, verbal action, and resistance. All of these are the common coping mechanisms used by LGBTQIA+ students in participating in academic programs and non-academic activities, and they are challenged to do their best in order to survive as far as gender preference is concerned.

Table 5

ANOVA on the significant difference in the extent of Academic programs and Non-academic activities when Respondents are grouped according to gender preference

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
ACAD MEAN	Between Groups	1.157	6	.193	1.353	.246	Do not reject H ₀	Not significant
	Within Groups	9.545	67	.142				
	Total	10.701	73					
NON-ACAD MEAN	Between Groups	.726	6	.121	.544	.773	Do not reject H ₀	Not significant
	Within Groups	14.891	67	.222				
	Total	15.617	73					

Table 5 shows the results of the ANOVA, which was employed to determine if there exists a significant difference in the extent of participation in academic programs and non-academic activities of the respondents when they are grouped according to gender preference. The analysis yielded f-value of 1.353 and 0.544 for academic programs and non-academic activities, respectively. It was shown that the p-value of 0.246 and 0.773, respectively, are beyond the 0.05 level of significance set for analysis. This means that the null hypothesis with respect to these variables is not rejected. Thus, it can be inferred that there is no significant difference in the extent of participation of the respondents in academic programs and non-academic activities across the different gender preferences when grouped according to the present gender preference that they presently claim.

Although there was no significant difference in the extent of participation in academic programs and non-academic activities across the different present gender preferences, the non-academic activities mean score was slightly higher than academic activity. Even if there's a little difference in their mean square value, the result of the ANOVA determined that the p-value was higher than the 0.05 level of significance. This means that present gender preference was not the differentiating factor for an individual's

participation in academic programs and non-academic activities when they were grouped according to their present gender preference.

As indicated in the result, LGBTQIA+ gender preference was not a general basis for participating in classroom and the school campus activities. It holds true to Ebenuwa (2010) that gender including age and financial status are not powerful indicators of academic performance but rather the fundamental and primary factors are the character and behaviors of the student inside and outside the class. Furthermore, the result of the present study contradicted the existing study by Herek (2009), which found that gay individuals are often more probable to experience gender biases than bisexual men and women or lesbians.

Table 6

ANOVA on the significant difference in the extent of academic programs and non-academic activities when respondents are grouped according to Age

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
ACAD MEAN	Between Groups	.693	4	.173	1.195	.321	Do not reject H ₀	Not significant
	Within Groups	10.008	69	.145				
	Total	10.701	73					
NON-ACAD MEAN	Between Groups	.879	4	.220	1.029	.399	Do not reject H ₀	Not significant
	Within Groups	14.738	69	.214				
	Total	15.617	73					

Table 6 presents the result of the ANOVA, which was employed to determine if there exists a significant difference in the extent of participation in academic programs and non-academic activities of the respondents when they are grouped according to age. The analysis yielded an f-value of 1.195 and 1.029 for academic programs and non-academic activities, respectively. It can be shown that the p-value of 0.321 and 0.399, respectively, are beyond the 0.05 level of significance set for analysis. This means that the null hypothesis with respect to these variables is not rejected. Thus, it can be inferred that there is no significant difference in the extent of participation of the respondents in academic programs and non-academic activities when respondents are grouped across different ages, as they presently claim.

The interpretation of the data resulted in no significant difference in the extent of participation in academic programs and non-academic activities across different age groups. However, the non-academic programs mean score is higher than the academic activities mean score. This means that even if there is a little difference in the mean square value, the result of the ANOVA shows that the p-value is higher than the level of significance. This can be inferred from the fact that age was not a differentiating factor for LGBTQIA+ students' participation in academic programs and non-academic activities when grouped according to the age that they presently claimed. It has proven by Ebenuwa (2010) that age including gender and financial status is not a powerful indicator of academic performance but rather the fundamental and primary factors are the character and behaviors of the student.

Table 7

ANOVA on the significant difference in the extent of academic programs and non-academic activities when respondents are grouped according to Year level

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Decision on H _o	Interpretation
ACAD MEAN	Between Groups	1.630	3	.543	4.193	.009	Reject H _o	Significant
	Within Groups	9.071	70	.130				
	Total	10.701	73					
NON-ACAD MEAN	Between Groups	.945	3	.315	1.503	.221	Do not reject H _o	Not significant
	Within Groups	14.672	70	.210				
	Total	15.617	73					

Table 7 presents the result of the ANOVA, which was employed to determine if there's a significant difference in the extent of participation in academic programs and non-academic activities of the respondents when they are grouped according to age. The analysis revealed an f-value of 4.193 and 1.503 for academic programs and non-academic activities, respectively. The academic programs has a p-value of 0.009, and the non-academic activities has a p-value of 0.221, respectively. This means that in the aspect of academic programs, the p-value is beyond the level of significance, whereas in non-academic activities, the p-value is above the level of significance. Thus, the analyses are respectively implied that in academic programs, the null hypothesis with respect to these variables is rejected, which means that there is a significant difference in the aspect of year level towards students in academic programs. On the other hand, in non-academic activities, the null hypothesis with respect to these variables is not rejected, which means that there is no significant difference in the extent of participation in non-academic activities when grouped according to the year level.

Although the analysis of these variables yields different numerical values, the level of significance, which is 0.05, can be used to identify the differentiating factors in their participation in academic programs and non-academic activities. In academic programs, when tested between groups, it falls into a 0.543 mean square, which is higher than non-academic activities between groups with a 0.315 mean square. Thus, this profoundly implied that the LGBTQIA+ students were more likely to participate in academic programs rather than non-academic activities across different year levels based on their current scholastic standing.

Despite different year levels, the LGBTQIA+ students have been involved in such activities intended for their personal benefits directed to them in order to have a better academic learning experience as well as a better social relationship with their classmates, friends, and instructors. According to Ullah & Wilson (2007), positive learning and building good connections with faculty and peers are more likely to have significance for students and can improve their academic performance.

Summary of Findings

This research study aimed to investigate the extent of participation of lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer, intersex, and asexual (LGBTQIA+) students in academic programs and non-academic activities. It further looked into the differences in gender preference, age, sex, year level, and course. With a total of 74 respondents from the Father Saturnino Urios University and the Caraga State University in Butuan City during the school year 2022-2023, the researcher has drawn the following summary of findings:

In the context of demographic profile, Sex Assigned at Birth found that male respondents were more dominant than females. It also revealed that gay respondents were the majority, followed by transgender women and lesbians. Age Group: The majority of the LGBTQIA+ students were ages 18 to 21, followed by 23 to 26 years old, of the total population size of the respondents. At the year level, the majority of the LGBTQIA+ students are graduating students, followed by the first year, third year, and second year of the total population of the respondents.

In terms of pursued academic programs, it was found that the majority of the LGBTQIA+ respondents were taking a Bachelor of Science in Forestry, followed by a Bachelor of Science in Social Worker at Caraga State University. In addition, the least number of respondents were taking courses in Bachelor of Arts in Political Science and Bachelor of Science in Education, followed by Bachelor of Science in Civil Engineering, Bachelor of Science in Nursing, Bachelor of Science in Accounting, Bachelor of Arts in Communication, Bachelor of Science in Hotel and Restaurant Management, Bachelor of Science in Information Technology, and Bachelor of Science in Business Administration at Father Saturnino Urios University.

The study found that in academic programs, LGBTQIA+ students were highly participative in group work activities, while in non-academic, activities were just enjoyed by LGBTQIA+ students being a part of the university.

The finding also showed that there was no manifestation of challenges encountered by the LGBTQIA+ students in participating the academic programs and non-academic activities in the Caraga State University, while there was a manifestation of challenges encountered by the LGBTQIA+ students in participating the academic programs and non-academic activities concerning LGBTQIA+ gender preferences at Father Saturnino Urios University.

The finding revealed that there is no significant difference in the extent of participation of the respondents in academic programs and non-academic activities across the different gender preference and age that they presently claimed. In relation to their year levels, the analyses are respectively inferred that in academic programs the null hypothesis with respect to these variables is rejected which denoted that there is significant difference. On the other hand, the non-academic activities show that the null hypothesis with respect to these variables is not rejected which means that there is no significant difference in the extent of participation in non-academic activities when grouped according to the year level that they presently claimed.

Through these findings, the researcher would like to recommend an action plan that pertained activities to propose to the Gender and Development Program in response to the needs of addressing gender issue encountered by some of the LGBTQIA+ students.

CONCLUSIONS

After a thorough analysis of the gathered data about the extent of participation of LGBTQIA+ students in academic programs and non-academic activities at FSUU and CSU for the school year 2022-2023, the researcher has drawn the following conclusions:

The existence of LGBTQIA+ people and their gender preferences are inevitable and have a high probability of increasing their population at the two universities at this time. In addition, Gender preferences, age groups, and year levels cannot be the general basis for LGBTQIA+ students' participation in academic programs and non-academic activities.

Also, adequate knowledge about LGBTQIA+ existence is not just a sufficient way of battling the feeling of being alienated and social isolation encountered by some of the LGBTQIA+ students in universities.

The findings also revealed that there is no significant difference in the extent of participation of the respondents in academic programs and non-academic activities when they are grouped according to gender preference and age. When grouped according to year level, there is a significant difference in LGBTQIA+ students' participation in

academic programs, but there is no significant difference in participation in non-academic activities.

On the basis of the findings of the study, the researcher would propose an Action Plan on Gender and Development Program for the Awareness of Sexual Orientation, Gender Identities, and Expression, or SOGIE.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Institutions may ensure a safe, gender sensitive, and gender-responsive environment to meet the needs of LGBTQIA+ students.

2. The LGBTQIA+ students may need to be dealt with in a gender-sensitive manner by other students, faculty, non-teaching personnel, and staff at the universities. One step is to educate students, instructors, non-teaching personnel, and staff about the existence of different gender preferences in the context of sexual orientation, gender identity, and expression of the students. This alternative may help students, faculty, non-teaching personnel, and staff to be socially aware and gender sensitive when treating the LGBTQIA+ individuals in the two universities in Butuan City.

3. There could be a collective effort between the school administrators, Gender and Development Program, Local Government, and Non-government organizations in conducting such activities in response to addressing gender issues related to gender preferences in the context of Sexual Orientation Gender Identity and Expression. Adequate knowledge about LGBTQIA+ existence is not just a sufficient way of battling the feeling of being alienated and social isolation encountered by some of the LGBTQIA+ students in universities.

4. Teachers, Non-teaching personnel, and staff may reexamine the existing gender sensitivity training instructional materials and revise them in consultation with members of the LGBTQIA+ community to include the SOGIE concept and LGBTQIA+ issues and concerns.

5. To propose an action plan to the Gender and Development Program to help conduct and spread awareness through lectures on Sexual Orientation, Gender Identity, and Expression, or SOGIE, symposiums, training, and seminars on gender diversity, gender sensitivity, gender mainstreaming, and gender neutrality for all students, faculty, non-teaching personnel, and staff, and hopes to have a better understanding of their existence that may help LGBTQIA+ students boost their confidence in being who they are and what they can do more in the aspects of academic programs and non-academic activities in the universities.

SOGIE AWARENESS ACTION PLAN 2023

Title. Be educated; Adequate knowledge on Sexual Orientation Gender Identity and Expression is a Milestone for having a Safe and Comfortable Zone through Embracing Diversity, Inclusivity, and Gender Sensitivity in the University.

Venue: Father Saturnino Urios University (FSUU) and Caraga State University (CSU)

1. Rationale

The research proposes Sexual Orientation Gender Identity and Expression or SOGIE Awareness Action Plan to propose to Gender and Development Program in the two universities. On the basis of these findings, the (LGBTQIA+) students are inevitably present and visible at Father Saturnino Urios University and Caraga State University Main Campus. However, their existence has been intertwined with different challenges in the face of normality in the concept of hetero-normativity in history. This zero tolerance has not been achieved yet due to the fact that a few students experience discomfort when dealing with people inside the university campus. This somehow hinders and challenges them from pursuing their goals in education. Based on the results of the study, there was a manifestation of challenges encountered by the LGBTQIA+ students in their

participation in academic programs and non-academic activities. Therefore, there is a great possibility of increasing the number of LGBTQIA+ individuals who will encounter alienation and social isolation. In such a situation and probability, the researcher proposes an action plan to ensure a better understanding of the SOGIE-Concept towards students, teachers, non-teaching personnel, and staff for an inclusive change, recognize diversity of gender preferences, and create a supportive learning environment.

Proposed Activities	Major Objectives	Time Frame	Target Participant	Person Involved	Success Indicator
Forum: An LGBTQIA+ Talk Series	To present and discuss Gender, Sex and SOGIE. To encourage young LGBTQIA+ Students to boost their confidence and self esteemed at all time.	1 st Month of the Beginning of the School Year	University Students	School Administrator Gender and Development Program Faculty and Staff	(To be Conducted)
Forums, Lectures, Seminars, Symposium	Endorsing openness and acceptance to breakdown the Culture of Bullying, Discrimination and Stigmatization intertwined into the life of LGBTQIA+ Students.	Whole School Year	University Students	School Administrator Gender and Development Program Faculty and Staff	(To be Reported and Identified)
Conduction of Gender Sensitivity Test will be held in the Classroom level and Faculty Offices By Department.	To encourage Gender Sensitivity Test for all students, faculty and Non-teaching Personnel to be assured that school learning environment is gender sensitive.	Whole School Year	University Students Faculty Non-teaching Personnel and Staff	School Administrator Gender and Development Program Faculty and Staff	(To be Reported and Identified)

Forums, Lectures, Seminars, Symposium	To ensure that the University is an LGBTQIA+ friendly, Gender Responsive to address all gender issues encountered by the LGBTQIA+ Students, Faculty and Non-teaching Personnel	Whole School Year	University Students Faculty Non-teaching Personnel and Staff	School Administrator, Gender and Development Program , Faculty and Staff, Guidance and Counselors	(To be Reported and Identified)
--	--	-------------------	--	--	---------------------------------

COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL STANDARDS

The researcher of the study ensured ethical consideration for the implementation of the data gathering procedure. The researcher obtained the approval of the research committee of Agusan Colleges Incorporated (ACI) before conducting the survey. Upon approval of the request for a survey, the researcher prepared the informed consent for the respondents of the study. This study focused on the extent of participation of LGBTQIA+ students in academic programs and non-academic activities at the two universities. The selection of respondents was limited since there were no groups of LGBTQIA+ students formally recognized at the two universities.

In data gathering, the researcher integrated a digital platform as the most convenient way to connect with and contact LGBTQIA+ students as subject respondents of the study. For instance, the researcher used digital platforms such as Facebook and Google Forms to send links to the respondents from these two universities, particularly Father Saturnino Urios University and Caraga State University in Butuan City. In this alternative, social media sites such as Facebook and Google Form links were utilized by the researcher. According to Franz et al. (2019), social media platforms provided an information-rich opportunity to reach diverse populations that would otherwise be difficult to identify. In that case, Facebook was the most dominant player in the social media landscape.

The survey was conducted virtually at the most convenient time for the respondents, using their Facebook accounts and group chats. The researcher was created a private Google Form link to explain the overview and the primary purpose of the survey to the respondents.

The Google Form link comprised two parts: Part 1. Demographic Profile and Part 2 Survey Questionnaire. After answering the demographic profile and survey questionnaire, the respondents completely submitted their respective responses. Once completed, respondents received duplicate answers with the certificate of participation in their respective emails.

Privacy is very crucial, this simply means that all of the data from the respondents should be kept with utmost confidentiality and be protected at all times for the safety of the respondents. In addition, the researcher ensures to follow the school's policy and aware about the importance of ethical standards and approval from the school research committee and experts to conduct this research study.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

With the deepest appreciation and sincerest thanks to the special persons for giving their time and effort in making this research possible:

Joanna B. Cuenca, PhD the Executive Vice President of Agusan Colleges Incorporated.

Nelia S. Raganas, PhD Dean of Graduate Studies, for undying support in this academic endeavor and as the statistician of the research study;

Rosemarie D. Paceño, PhD thesis adviser, for imparting expertise, and giving persistent guidance and advise to further improve the manuscript;

The thesis committee member, Fe M. Dela Cruz, PhD for constructive and significant suggestions and recommendations that contributed to the improvement of this research study;

The three experts: Editha D. Naldo, DM former Gender and Development focal person at Bukidnon State University, Rodello D. Pepito, EdD Director of the Center of Language and Culture at the College of Arts and Sciences in Bukidnon State University; and Prof. Rocelito A. Duropan, Assistant Professor III at the Behavioral Sciences Department in Central Mindanao University, for the efforts in validating the content of the research instrument;

To the LGBTQIA+ students of the Father Saturnino Urios University (FSUU) and the Caraga State University (CSU) for voluntarily participating in the study as respondents.

REFERENCES

- Astin, A. W. (1984). Student involvement: A developmental theory for higher education. *Journal of college student personnel*, 25(4), 297-308.
- Barker, M-J., & Scheele, J. (2016). *Queer: A graphic history*. London: Icon Books, Ltd. Pages, pp. 1-22; 25-50; 79-90.
- Bekkering, E., Ward, T. (2020) Class participation and student performance: A tale of two courses. Retrieved June 11, 2022, from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1258148.pdf>
- Burnes, T. R., & Singh, A. A. (2016). "Gay in the bank, queer in the streets": The intersection of LGBTQQ and social class identities. *Journal of LGBT Issues in Counseling*, 10(1), 55-71.
- Butler, J. (1988). *Performative Acts and Gender Constitution: An Essay in Phenomenology and Feminist Theory*. *Theatre Journal*, 40(4), 519-531. doi:10.2307/3207893
- Creswell, J. W. (2010). Mapping the developing landscape of mixed methods research. In A. Tashakkori & C. Teddlie (Eds.), *SAGE handbook of mixed methods in social and behavioral research* (2nd ed., pp. 45–68). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, mixed methods approaches*. California, CA: SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Ebenuwa-Okoh, Evelyn. (2010). Influence of Age, Financial Status, and Gender on Academic Performance among Undergraduates. *Journal of Psychology*. 1.10.1080/09764224.2010.11885451.
- Flores, A. (2019). *Social Acceptance of LGBT People in 174 Countries, 1981 to 2017*. The Williams Institute, Los Angeles, CA.
- Foreman, K. (2018, July 30). What is queer theory? Retrieved July 2019 from <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E7P1cofLIU>

- Franz, D., Marsh, H. E., Chen, J. I., & Teo, A. R. (2019). Using Facebook for Qualitative Research: A Brief Primer. *Journal of medical Internet research*, 21(8), e13544. <https://doi.org/10.2196/13544>
- Gay, L. R. (1987) *Educational research: Competencies for analysis and application*. 3rd. edn. London: Merrill Publishing.
- Glen, S. (2023). "Snowball Sampling: Definition, Advantages and Disadvantages" From *StatisticsHowTo.com: Elementary Statistics for the rest of us!* <https://www.statisticshowto.com/probabilityandstatistics/statisticsdefinitions/snowball-sampling/>
- Holdsworth, R. (2000). Schools that create real roles of value for young people. *Prospects*, 30(3), 349-362.
- Jagose, A. (1996). *Queer theory: An introduction*. NYU Press. Chapter One: Introduction and Chapter Seven: Queer
- Kang, M., Lessard, D., Heston, L., & Nordmarken, S. (2017, June 30). The sex/gender/sexuality system. *Introduction to Women Gender Sexuality Studies*. Retrieved November 4, 2022, from <https://openbooks.library.umass.edu/introwgss/chapter/the-sexgendersexuality-system/>
- Kay, C. M. (2022). *Challenges of Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer, Intersex, and Asexual (LGBTQIA) Students in Higher Education* (Doctoral dissertation, Walden University).
- McElhill, D. (2006). Philippines to vote on gay law. *Pink News*. Retrieved 4 September 2013 from <http://www.pinknews.co.uk/2006/08/15/philippines-to-vote-on-gay-law/>.
- Munyuki, C., & Vincent, L. (2018). Strangers "at home": Gay, lesbian and bisexual students' strategies for resisting heteronormativity in university residence life. *South African Journal of Higher Education*, 32(3), 64-80.
- Narayanaswamy, V. R., & Harinarayana, N. S. (2016). Online survey tools: A case study of google forms. Retrieved March 7, 2022, from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/NarayanaswamyVasanthaRaju/publication/326831738_Online_survey_tools_A_case_study_of_Google_Forms/links/5c1f9de492851c22a341c79c/Online-survey-tools-A-case-study-of-Google-Forms.pdf
- Rankin, S., Weber, G., Blumenfeld, W., & Frazer, S (2010). 2010 state of higher education for lesbian, gay, bisexual & transgender people. Charlotte, NC: CampusPride.
- Schwartz, C. S., & Sinicrope, R. (2013). Prospective elementary teachers' perceptions of gender differences in children's attitudes toward mathematics. *School Science and Mathematics*, 113(8), 410-416. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ssm.12045>
- Ullah, H., & Wilson, M. A. (2007). Students' academic success and its association to student involvement with learning and relationships with faculty and peers. *College Student Journal*, 41(4), 1192+. <https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/A172978018/AONE?u=anon~efa9a61e&sid=googleScholar&xid=010131d6>
- UNDP & USAID. (2014). *Being LGBT in Asia: The Philippines Country Report*. Bangkok.